

Food Memories Report

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D3.1 Overview

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Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	ICH	Intangible Cultural Heritage
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Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
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Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
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Executive Summary

The present document is the “Food Memories Report,” which describes the development process, rationale, methods, pilots, initial findings, and next steps for D 3.1 “Food Memories Manual.” This task was completed by WP3: INGREDIENTS for further consultation and replication by WP4 and WP5. Sections of the report will also inform further WP3 and Food Memories dissemination output.

This report includes the initial template for the Food Memories Manual, found in Appendix II. The initial template refers to a guide or “manual” for Food Memories, a core participatory methodology using creative life-writing, narrative inquiry, and cooking exercises to explore and elicit emerging adults’ food memories. The template will be developed into a Manual for integration in the RELISH platform and further exploitation.

All the above is completed under the direction of Fundació Alícia (FA), with Roskilde University (RUC) and Atlantic Technological University (ATU).

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

Fundació Alícia (FA) leads Work Package 3: INGREDIENTS. FA leads Food Memories, a thematic group with Roskilde University (RUC) and Atlantic Technological University (ATU). The objective of Food Memories is to build models of connection between food traditions, food culture, storytelling, outreach and education.

1.1 Description of the document

This document outlines the development of the Food Memories Workshops, a core participatory methodology within RELISH. Under this framework, the document outlines how Food Memories uses creative life-writing, narrative inquiry, and—when applicable—cooking-as-inquiry (Brady 2011) to explore how personal food memories illuminate broader patterns of cultural identity, belonging, and continuity that link to an action-based conceptualisation of food as Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH) (UNESCO 2024). The workshop design positions participants, here “emerging adults,” as co-creators of knowledge: their stories, sensory recollections, and food practices reveal emotional and cultural dimensions that enhance conventional research approaches.

This workshop examines food memories as powerful anchors of identity and belonging, using creative writing, recollection, and cooking as pathways to engage with Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH). The workshop methodology is grounded in participatory, reflective, and experiential learning, combining creative writing, visual mapping, dialogue, and hands-on cooking. Participants are guided through structured exercises that activate food memories using sensory prompts, journaling, and narrative reconstruction, allowing them to trace culinary knowledge transmitted through family, community, and migration. Visual tools such as memory maps support the organisation of recollections across time and place, while facilitated

discussions encourage relational learning through comparison, listening, and shared reflection on similarities and differences in food traditions.

Methodologically, the workshop unfolds over two to four consecutive days or in an extended modular format, enabling both collective sessions and independent work between meetings. Activities may include mapping individual foodscapes, collaborative memory recollection, interviews with family members, and iterative recipe development that translates memory into embodied practice. Collaborative cooking sessions function as sites of co-creation, where participants test, adapt, and document recipes while collectively activating Intangible Cultural Heritage. The approach emphasises process over product, fostering speculative thinking about future food practices, sustainability, and emerging rituals through experimentation, dialogue, and documentation.

1.2 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable

This phase of the workshop focuses on emerging adults, many of whom participate in European mobility programs (including Erasmus+). Their experiences offer insight into how young people navigate culinary identity and cultural heritage while living abroad.

Appended to this report is the initial template, “Food Memories as Living Heritage,” that will be used, in consultation with WP 4 and WP 5, in four workshops taking place in Spring and Fall 2026 (specific dates to be determined by the partners). Two workshops will be held at Roskilde University (Denmark) and the University of Milan (Italy), which will include one day of narrative production and speculative thinking exercises, without cooking sessions. The next two workshops, to be held at Atlantic Technical University–Galway (Ireland) and Fundació Alícia (Spain), will include one day of narrative production and speculative thinking exercises, and a second day of cooking exercises based on recipes proposed by the participants.

2 Justification

This section describes the Food Memories Manual and workshop template justification for generating data and input for the RELISH platform, as well as its value for scholarly and independent use for RELISH target audiences.

2.1 Background

Food Memories originated as a grassroots cultural initiative in Denmark to create inclusive and participatory programs to support migrants and newcomers in exploring how food, memory, and identity intersect in everyday life (Savinetti, Kristiansen, and Martínez 2020).

Earlier iterations of the program employed creative writing, mapping, and reflective dialogue; participants examined how their culinary practices adapted to new environments, how family traditions were remembered or transformed, and how sensory memories supported feelings of belonging. These iterations led to multilingual exhibitions and contributed to national-level heritage initiatives, including the UNESCO-funded project “LIVIND” exploring forms of living heritage.

Early findings from the initial iterations demonstrated the method’s broader relevance to understanding cultural sustainability and inclusion. RELISH integrates this method to build models of connection between food traditions, food culture, storytelling, outreach and education, particularly for target audiences and internal partners who research with emerging adults in Europe.

The Food Memories, led by Fundació Alícia, together with University of Roskilde and ATU-Galway, designed and prototyped the workshops during three pilots conducted in May, June, and October 2025. The following report content identifies the Food Memories development process, early findings, and proposals and plans for further internal use and broader exploitability. Plans include: a proposed template for replicability of the workshops within RELISH; systematically scaling and adapting the method to support a wider range of participants across diverse European contexts.

The Food Memories Manual and narrative and storytelling participatory methods add richness to the qualitative approach of RELISH’s mission. Lewis and Hildebrandt suggest that it is “people’s everyday stories—their storytelling about work, practice, or experiences—that form a treasure trove of data that can augment understandings of complex human actions and interactions” (Lewis and Hildebrandt 2019, 4). Storytelling, as participant-led knowledge of creation through life-writing, illuminates how culinary heritage operates as a form of ICH. The method shows how mobility and migration reshape recipes, tastes, and kitchen practices. As a RELISH task, the method will also generate narrative and audiovisual material for the RELISH digital platform.

2.2 Relevance, alignment with RELISH objectives, and expected outcomes

The integration of Food Memories within RELISH directly supports the project's mission to connect people, places, and practices through Europe's culinary heritage. Its participatory, narrative-driven approach adds significant value for internal use and project results by:

- **Bridging research and lived experience**—bringing forward qualitative, emotion-rich data that deepens understanding of food heritage as ICH
- **Highlighting the impact of mobility and migration**—exploring how recipes, ingredients, and techniques evolve through cross-cultural encounters
- **Empowering community voices**—especially those of women, migrants, and minorities, aligning with RELISH's inclusivity goals
- **Enriching the digital infrastructure**—providing content and methodologies for the RELISH platform, fostering participatory digital heritage practices

2.2.1 Rationale

Conducting the workshops with and without the cooking sessions provides insights into how the manual can be useful for spaces with different or limited facilities. The cooking sessions also offer comparative insights on how integrating cooking exercises can create an embodied connection between writing, memory, and the sensory experience of preparing and sharing food.

This phase aims to explore the extent to which everyday food practices relate to, depend on, preserve, and innovate upon inherited culinary culture. Rather than centring on specific recipes, the workshop focus will be on writing and storytelling as reflective and co-creative acts that help participants articulate how their daily lives engage with, reinterpret, and transform Europe's culinary traditions.

Importantly, this phase also incorporates a forward-looking dimension, which the cooking session is specifically designed to activate in line with the project's aims, it invites participants not only to deepen their understanding of culinary food heritage, but also to consider how it can be mobilised, used, or gain importance in the future.

The first narrative session invites participants to revisit memories and reflect on the past (how family practices, migration experiences, or sensory memories have shaped their culinary identities). The cooking session provides a space to consider how these practices may evolve in the future. Through the embodied act of cooking together,

participants explore not only what they have inherited, but also what they imagine carrying forward, modifying, or redefining in response to changing lifestyles, new environments, or emerging social and cultural influences.

In this way, Food Memories supports an understanding of food heritage as dynamic and future-oriented: something participants actively remake, negotiate, and project into the years ahead, rather than merely preserve.

It opens a space for participants to attend to their food knowledge, family traditions, and learned culinary techniques with renewed awareness. Connecting with gastronomy in a mindful and emotionally engaged way—often in forms they might not have accessed otherwise—the exercise becomes a powerful experiential mechanism. It activates memory while also consolidating knowledge and supporting forward-looking decision-making, grounding reflection not only in what is remembered but in how food practices may be consciously carried forward and adapted.

Through these participatory workshops, Food Memories will:

- **Generate empirical insight** into how young Europeans relate to food heritage—not assuming that emotional or cultural attachments necessarily exist but providing a space where such relationships may be revealed, nuanced, confirmed, or even challenged.
- **Function as a reflective practice**, allowing participants to become aware of processes of continuity, disruption, and change in their culinary experiences and in the ways, they interpret (or distance themselves from) inherited food practices.
- **Act as a co-creative process** through which participants collectively explore what European culinary heritage can mean today—not as a fixed or universally shared inheritance, but as a dynamic, diverse, and sometimes contested field shaped by mobility, hybridity, and lived experience.

The materials and narratives generated through these workshops will be integrated into the RELISH digital platform, contributing to its development as a dynamic and interactive space for engaging with food heritage, and providing opportunities for ongoing analysis, dissemination, and educational use.

2.2.2 *Contribution to Project Results*

The Food Memories Manual is a project result in the form of a transferable method for multiple RELISH partners to elicit data on the relationship between identity, experience of mobility and migration, and culinary heritage in tandem with other project qualitative and quantitative methods (such as surveys, interviewing, and participant-observation). The Initial Template is attached to this report, and further iterations will focus on refining, scaling, and further exploiting the method for internal and external use. The manual offers a scalable and inclusive method transferable between research and community spaces that can be deployed to generate insights on changing trends, relationships, and transitions in communities through food-related narratives and cooking exercises.

WP3's objectives primarily comprise data collection activities. Food Memories workshop data—in the form of written reflections, illustrations, recordings, interviews, facilitator observations, and recipes developed—produced by Food Memories will be integrated into the RELISH platform and interpreted and analysed by project partners, in tandem with other project results. Selected data will be publicly accessible through the platform, preliminarily planned in the form of interactive storytelling and visual guides.

2.2.3 *Expected Outcomes*

This report and manual will inform further communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities to reach selected RELISH Target Audiences. Target audiences here are categorised as “Mediators”—cultural and educational figures, such as instructors, organisers, and researchers who connect groups of stakeholders, such as young people, migrant communities, and professionals in knowledge production, exchange, and transmission settings.

Expected benefits include sharing participatory knowledge and skills on how to:

- Connect to under-represented food communities and populations
- Elicit grounded narrative and data
- Integrate novel participatory cooking exercises in research and programming

Communication activities comprise social media outreach and campaigns reporting on the effectiveness and applicability of the Manual for target audiences. These are phased as:

- 1) **Generating Interest** (showing samples of exercise activities and early findings and testimonials)
- 2) **Eliciting Input** (through additional workshops and trials with selected audiences)

Dissemination activities comprise:

- Academic publications and presentations on the development and preliminary findings of the Food Memories manual
- Offering an early, Open-Access (OA) version of the manual to be distributed to target audiences
- Further published editions integrated into the RELISH platform and/or other relevant outlets

3 Timeline Overview

Figure 1: Food Memories timeline at-a-glance

3.1 “Stage 1: Food Memories Initial Template and Pilots” overview

In Months 1 to 4 partners conducted a literature review of participatory methods with food and research on food, storytelling, and identity. In Month 5, partners developed an initial set of question prompts, narrative exercises, cooking exercise guides, and procedures for data collection and recording. The early template was presented to participating partners at ATU, with FA, RUC, and Durham University (UDUR) in attendance. Timelines and the initial template were revised. In Months 5, 6 and 10, pilots were conducted at FA, with ATU partners in attendance, to address any gaps or issues with the guide and its implementation. Early data was generated from pilots with ERASMUS+ participants, and preliminary audiovisual materials were gathered. In Month 12 partners finalised the initial template (D3.1) and this accompanying report in preparation for Stage 2: Workshop Development and Implementation for RELISH.

Partners decided on four workshops with project partner institutions and facilities (outlined below in 3.2: Stage 2).

3.2 “Stage 2: Workshop Development and Implementation for RELISH” overview

From Month 16 to Month 25 Food Memories will conduct a series of four creative life-writing workshops with emerging adults in different European contexts. Two of these workshops will include a second day of cooking sessions, and two without cooking sessions. From Month 9 to Month 27 partners will meet in consultation with WP 4 and 5 to refine the template and finalise cooking session dates, based on partner and institutional availability.

3.3 “Stage 3: Integrating Food Memories into Platform” overview

Stage 3 focuses on the structured integration of the Food Memories manual and related activities into the RELISH platform through close collaboration with WP4, WP5, and the IST team. This stage addresses both interface design and the underlying coordination, timing, iterative analysis, and co-development processes, ensuring that design decisions are grounded in collaborative planning and cross-work package alignment. Initial coordination meetings with FA, ATU, RUC, and Milan will take place on an ongoing basis and be completed by mid-January 2026 to establish shared timelines, roles, and integration strategies. Follow-up working meetings will be held with FA, ATU, and RUC in Spring 2026, and with Milan in Fall 2026, aligning platform integration with local pilots and institutional calendars.

In collaboration with IST, a pilot initiative will test culinary cultural activities as storytelling tools within the platform. This will include the selection of an MA-level student in January 2026 to support the pilot, followed by a prototyping phase in Spring 2026 and a development and testing phase in Summer 2026 (tentative). Participant recruitment will be coordinated at FA, ATU, and RUC, with the first pilot implemented at FA from 9–15 February 2026. This pilot will involve facilitation, structured data collection, and initial analysis, with findings feeding directly into iterative refinement of both the activities and their platform integration ahead of subsequent pilots at ATU and RUC. Analysis and interpretation will be conducted continuously in collaboration with WP4, WP5, and IST, ensuring methodological coherence and meaningful translation of community-based food memory practices into digital learning and engagement tools.

4 Completed Work: Stage 1 Full Description

In May 2025, a meeting was held at ATU with the partners responsible for designing and implementing the workshops: ATU hosts, FA, RUC, and UDUR. Over two working days, the group jointly developed the script for the narrative workshops and conceptualised the cooking sessions—their rationale, necessity, and procedures for conducting and data-gathering during facilitation.

During the narrative workshops, the group first reviewed and jointly agreed on the overall methodology and the structure of the exercises. It was then agreed to incorporate a final exercise focused on identifying or creating a recipe that would later be prepared during the cooking session. Additionally, participants identified a need to orient part of the qualitative data collection towards the foresight objectives of WP9, which are linked to the construction of future scenarios.

In parallel, work progressed on defining the structure and objectives of the cooking sessions, which constitute a novel component of the project and therefore require a shared conceptualisation. The team addressed both conceptual aspects (the added value of cooking as a methodological complement to narrative work, and the specific learning and analytical objectives) and practical considerations related to the session implementation. Various scenarios were examined depending on factors, such as the number of recipes and participants, characteristics of the available space, and exercise format (a pre-selected recipe or one co-created during the narrative session).

Key methodological elements were also established. This included the need to schedule the cooking session 23 days after the narrative workshop to allow time for

logistical preparation (purchasing ingredients, materials, etc.), as well as defining the role of facilitators and the required professional profile.

Following this meeting, FA carried out three pilots of the cooking methodology: two focused exclusively on the culinary session, without a narrative session, and a third integrated the full format, combining the narrative workshop with the cooking session.

4.1 Participant Recruitment

Participants for the pilots were recruited through institutional mailing lists, social media announcements, and direct outreach to university groups. Recruitment proved challenging, particularly for the local population, and required multiple rounds of communication. The most effective channels were targeted in Instagram posts and personalised invitations circulated through university networks. To ensure commitment, compensation for participants' time, economic remuneration was offered. This stipend acknowledged the intensive nature of the workshops and was essential for achieving adequate participation levels.

4.2 Pilot Outcomes

4.2.1 Pilot 1 – May 2025

Seven international students and young professionals participated in the session (Chilean, Spanish, Mexican, and Brazilian). Participants were already acquainted with one another and had diverse culinary backgrounds: some cooked regularly for themselves or friends, while others mainly engaged in cooking for special occasions or family traditions; two participants were professional chefs.

As this was a pilot implementation, the session did not include the preceding narrative-writing day originally planned in the methodology. Instead, a thematic discussion was held prior to the cooking exercise. The primary objective was to test the operational aspects of the cooking-based food memory exercise and to obtain an overall assessment of the methodology's strengths and limitations, with the aim of refining and adjusting it for subsequent implementations.

Three recipes were selected and prepared, each representing a food memory shared by one participant:

- *Tres leches*—a memory associated with childhood. Highlights the importance of letting it cool and technical issues such as soaking the cake progressively.

Figure 2: Pilot 1 cooking session

- *Zucchini, leek, and basil pasta*—a dish associated with her cooking teacher, whom she holds in high esteem. She now prepares this dish for the people she cares about.
- *Cuscús paulista*—a recipe from São Paulo; the participant emphasised the importance of using corn flake flour. While the remaining ingredients are easily replaceable, this one is not.

The pilot generated a set of primary and secondary materials to support both immediate methodological refinement and subsequent cross-site comparability. As the narrative-writing day was not implemented in this pilot, the data collection focused on materials produced during the thematic discussion and the cooking exercise.

PRIMARY MATERIALS (COLLECTED DURING THE SESSION)

- Participant-written recipes (three recipes), including any handwritten notes and clarifications provided during preparation. – See Figures 3 & 4 for original and transcribed participant recipe sample, presented in its original language

Figure 3: Recipe #3 participant worksheet (left) and family photo (right)

Figure 4: Transcribed recipe from Pilot 1, Recipe #3: Cuscús paulista

RECIPe 3: CUSCÚS PAULISTA

Ingredientes:

- 1 lata de atún en aceite, escurrido y desmenuzado
- 1 lata de sardinas en aceite, escurridas y desmenuzadas
- 2 dientes de ajo, finamente picados
- 1 cebolla blanca, brunoise
- 1 puerro, parte blanca, finamente picado
- 1 frasco de palmitos, escurridos y cortados en rodajas
- 6 tomates sin piel, sin semillas, cortados en concassé
- 1 pimiento morrón rojo, asado, pelado y cortado en tiras
- Aceitunas verdes al gusto, en rodajas
- 2 huevos cocidos, cortados en rodajas para decoración
- Guisantes verdes (arvejas), al gusto
- Orégano seco, al gusto
- Perejil fresco picado y hojas enteras para decoración
- Harina de maíz en copos (tipo flocada), cantidad necesaria
- 1 taza de agua (240 ml) para hidratar la harina
- 1 litro de agua (para la preparación general)
- Aceite de oliva extra virgen, cantidad necesaria

Elaboración:

1) Mise en place:

Preparar todos los ingredientes: pelar y concassear los tomates; asar, pelar y filetear el pimiento; picar finamente ajo, cebolla y puerro; escurrir y desmenuzar las conservas; cocer los huevos y cortar en rodajas.

2) Decoración del molde:

Engrasar ligeramente un molde con aceite de oliva. Decorar la base con rodajas de huevo duro, tiras de pimiento, guisantes, rodajas de palmito y hojas de perejil fresco. Reservar.

3) Sofrito:

En una sartén amplia, calentar aceite de oliva y saltear la cebolla, el ajo y el puerro hasta que estén translúcidos. Añadir el pimiento fileteado y continuar salteando.

4) Incorporación de pescados:

Agregar el atún y las sardinas desmenuzadas. Cocinar por unos minutos, removiendo bien para integrar los sabores.

5) Tomate y vegetales:

Incorporar el tomate concassé y cocinar hasta que se deshaga ligeramente. Añadir el palmito y los guisantes. Condimentar con orégano y rectificar sal si es necesario.

- 6) **Hidratación y cocción:**
 Verter el litro de agua y llevar a ebullición. Una vez que hierva, añadir poco a poco la harina de maíz flocada, removiendo constantemente para evitar grumos. Agregar también la taza de agua adicional para ayudar na hidratação da farinha. La mezcla debe quedar húmeda, con textura de masa espesa pero no seca.
- 7) **Montaje:**
 Verter la preparación caliente en el molde decorado, sin compactar en exceso. Alisar la superficie y dejar reposar hasta que tome consistencia.
- 8) **Finalización:**
 Una vez frío y firme, desmoldar cuidadosamente sobre un plato o bandeja de presentación. Decorar con hojas frescas de perejil.

- Facilitator field notes and structured cooking observations, documenting key decision points, embodied actions, and tacit knowledge (e.g., sensory judgements, substitutions, implicit rules).

PROCESSED MATERIALS (COMPILED AFTER THE SESSION)

- Preliminary analytical framework and analysis table, prepared *ex ante* as a facilitation and observation guide (categories/concepts to be explored), and reviewed *ex post* to assess whether the expected analytical categories were evidenced in the pilot and to identify emergent themes requiring inclusion or adjustment.

Table 1: Developed categories and concepts framework from Pilot 1

Dish / recipe / preparation	
Ingredients	
Learning and transmission of knowledge	
Preparation	
Consumption	
Future perspective	
Cultural heritage and legacy	

Sustainability	
Flexibility	
Memory	
Other	

ANALYTICAL AND OPERATIONAL OUTPUTS

- Methodological learning notes synthesising strengths, limitations, and implementation issues identified during the pilot, and documenting concrete adjustments to be applied in the next implementation (e.g., facilitation timing, prompts, sequencing, observation focus).

Note: Audio/audiovisual recordings and photographic documentation were not systematically collected in this pilot. Where available in future pilots, these data types will support additional triangulation.

4.2.2 Pilot 2 – June 2025

Four Catalan students participated in the second workshop. Only two participants were previously acquainted, and none had formal culinary training; their cooking experience ranged from occasional home cooking to more regular practice.

Unlike the first pilot, this session allowed for a longer discussion phase. This additional time was used to test the Workshop and Survey Design with Data Collection (Task 3.2) and to provide participants with a broader introduction to the overall project and to the Food Memories methodology. Moreover, the methodological issues identified during the first exercise had already been addressed and adjusted in this implementation.

Due to time constraints and in order to maintain better control of the group dynamics, only one recipe was prepared:

- *Fricandó* – a recipe from the participant’s grandmother that she often cooks; a similar version found online was provided, with the family adaptations detailed.

The second pilot generated a broader set of materials than Pilot 1, as the session included an extended discussion phase and a test of the workshop and survey

instruments (Task 3.2). In addition, the methodological adjustments identified in Pilot 1 were implemented, allowing the collection of more controlled and structured observations.

Figure 5: Pilot 2 Cooking Session

PRIMARY MATERIALS (COLLECTED DURING THE SESSION)

- Recipe documentation for the prepared dish: including the online reference version provided by the participant and the documented family adaptations clarified during the session.

Figure 6: Participant recipe selection transcript

Below are the recipes suggested by the participant:

PBF: My recipes are *fricandó* with white rice, hamburger sandwich, gnocchi with pesto and marinated chicken, and butter chicken curry!

In the end, the fricandó recipe was chosen. Below are the participant's notes about the recipe:

PBF: I'll send you a link with a recipe that is very similar to the one I use, so you can take it as guidance.

Mine isn't exactly this one, because I follow the one I learned from my grandmother. The main differences are that I use broth (meat or vegetable), and before adding the meat back I blend the vegetable sofrito a little (sometimes adding a carrot while the vegetables cook). Then I add the meat and let it reduce.

- Facilitator field notes and structured cooking observations: using the updated guide/template to capture key decision points, embodied actions, and tacit knowledge (e.g., sensory judgements, family rules, substitutions, constraints).
- Audio and/or audiovisual recordings of the discussion and cooking process (subject to consent and equipment availability).

Figure 7: Screenshot from audiovisual materials generated in Pilot 2

Figure 8: Findings to implement in manual from Pilots 1 and 2)

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS (FROM PILOT 1 AND 2)

There must be two main roles: the observer, who takes notes, and the facilitator, who leads the workshop.

The first finding we noticed is that the facilitator, due to being immersed in conducting the cooking/recipe session, does not have the time or capacity to take notes while also guiding the activity. This issue is resolved by the presence of an external observer, who should record everything that happens throughout the recipe preparation process—both the procedural aspects and the conversations or narratives that emerge during the session.

It should be noted that the facilitator may be accompanied by a cook. The cook contributes culinary knowledge and can both assist in carrying out the recipe and ask questions about what is happening from a culinary perspective—questions that might arise from curiosity, strangeness, particularities, or the need for clarification. This teamwork is important.

The second finding refers to the need to carry out a complete pilot—that is, both narrative + cooking. We must be able to observe how the flow of information shifts from one session to the other. It is important to see whether participant interaction during the cooking session changes, or whether their discourse becomes more complex, considering that they have already participated in the narrative session.

The third finding, for the case at hand, concerns the type of recipe chosen. We have two options: selecting an existing recipe through consensus, or creating an invented recipe crafted by the participants themselves during the writing workshop. It has been observed that if the recipe originates from a single participant and must then be shared with the group, a dynamic emerges where one person monopolises the discourse, while the others tend to take on the role of spectators.

The fourth finding has to do with time. There must be no rush. The session should allow enough time for a relaxed conversation, without being constrained by a strict schedule. In this sense, very complex preparations (for example, making fresh pasta or bread dough) should be prepared in advance.

ANALYTICAL AND OPERATIONAL OUTPUTS

- Pilot debrief and refinement log: documenting remaining implementation constraints, and any additional adjustments required for subsequent workshops. Synthesising strengths, limitations, and implementation issues identified during the pilot, and documenting concrete adjustments to be applied in the next implementation. – See Figure 8

PROCESSED MATERIALS (COMPILED AFTER THE SESSION)

- Updated facilitation and observation template, reflecting the methodological refinements implemented after Pilot 1. – *See Appendix II for final version*

EARLY FINDINGS FROM PILOTS 1 & 2

In both pilots, the recipes reflected the history, identity, or individual food memories of some of the participants. The initial methodology focused on the experience of one individual and the recipe was the one identified through a simple interview. This revealed certain limitations that played out in the cooking session. While cooking the conversation tended to revolve around the person who contributed to the recipe, while the remaining participants assumed a more peripheral role.

As a result, the methodology was adjusted: **the recipe would now be agreed upon or co-created by all participants**, ensuring that each person would have an equivalent role in the cooking dynamic and foster more equitable participation.

4.2.3 Pilot 3 – October 2025

This was the first implementation to apply the full two session workshop structure, comprising a narrative-writing session followed by a cooking session. As a result, it generated a more comprehensive set of qualitative materials, capturing both narrative production and embodied cooking practices, and enabling a stronger basis for triangulation across workshop components. Five young Catalan women participated, none of whom knew each other beforehand. Their culinary backgrounds varied: some cooked regularly at home, while others had more limited experience. This pilot followed the complete two-session structure—one narrative session and one cooking session—with a one-day interval to accommodate logistical preparation.

During the narrative session, participants engaged in visual mapping and creative writing exercises. Following the writing session, a facilitated discussion allowed participants to share their work and identify common ground, leading to the collective identification and co-creation of a recipe agreed upon by all participants, which then served as the basis for a speculative exercise on future recipes and the cooking session. The selected recipes were mushroom croquettes and plantain croquettes with *quesillo latino*.

Figure 9: Visual material from Pilot 3

PRIMARY MATERIALS (COLLECTED DURING THE WORKSHOP SESSIONS)

- Visual mapping artefacts (see Figure 9) produced by participants during the narrative session, including individual maps, diagrams, and other graphic representations of food memories. These artefacts reflected diverse structuring strategies, such as temporal mappings organised around seasonal cycles, relational mappings centred on family roles and matriarchal figures, and material-process mappings tracing food harvesting, transformation, preservation, and consumption. Across these materials, recurring analytical categories (e.g., location, time, material culture, social roles) were identifiable as key dimensions through which food production and consumption were framed as Cultural Heritage.

Figure 10: Creative writing outputs from Pilot 3

- Creative writing outputs (life-writing texts) generated in response to the visual mapping exercise and subsequent group discussion. Participants produced short, unstructured texts written in the first or second person, in Catalan or Spanish, and using an automatic writing approach that privileged memory recall over formal coherence. The resulting texts varied in form and content, ranging from introspective mnemonic narratives prompted by sensory memories (e.g., smell) to relational accounts detailing family interactions, caregiving practices, and the distribution of roles during food preparation and shared meals. Collectively, these texts foregrounded intergenerational knowledge transmission, care through food, and the impact of social and environmental change on family food practices. – See Figure 10 for examples
- Group discussion notes, documenting shared reflections on the visual maps and written narratives, and capturing contextual information regarding the meanings, values and social relations associated with the food memories discussed.

- Collaboratively defined recipe, co-created by participants during the narrative session and collectively agreed as a shared reference point for the subsequent cooking session.
- Audio and/or audiovisual recordings and photographic documentation: photos and recording of narrative discussions and the cooking process, where consent was provided and equipment was available.
- Updated facilitation guide and script: for both the narrative and the cooking sessions. – See Appendix I

Figure 11: Pilot 3 visual documentation example

EARLY FINDINGS FROM PILOTS 3

The earlier pilots omitted the narrative sessions because the team was focusing on observing and identifying how the cooking sessions would develop and what adjustments would need to take place to make them productive, safe and methodologically appropriate. At this point the focus was on embodied knowledge and aural storytelling to identify how it could relate to the written sessions that had

already been tested in previous iterations of the workshops. Memories team hypothesised that the reduced depth in participant storytelling during cooking activities—particularly the limited elaboration on memories—might have resulted from the absence of this initial reflective phase. Implementing the full two-session format in Pilot 3 allowed a clearer assessment of the added value of the narrative component, confirming that memory mapping and writing significantly enriched participants' engagement and the quality of their contributions during the cooking session.

In addition, a preliminary audiovisual piece illustrating both the promotional potential and the practical implementation of the workshop format was produced.

5 Theoretical Approach

This section outlines the conceptual and culinary approaches for developing the Food Memories initial template and methodology. These approaches will inform how the Manual will be integrated in the platform and dissemination materials and opportunities initially planned by the team.

5.1 Narrative approach: Conceptual justification supported by existing evidence

Food and eating involve the interplay between 1) the individual experience of various registers of taste, and 2) collective references to historically constructed practices acknowledged as regional and national cuisines (Hedegaard 2018). It may seem straightforward to identify a recipe as belonging to a specific tradition, but it raises a key question: How can individual recollection be reconciled with historical memory from the context of an anonymous and collective 'we' (Ricoeur 2000)? The interplay between individual and collective memory is fundamental to understanding how recipes work in the context of cultural heritage.

One way of developing a method to understand this interplay is through narrative inquiry. In general, narrative inquiry involves eliciting and exploring individual perspectives and experience through dialogue, writing sessions, visual mapping, etc. It is based on the assertion that narratives represent experience and can be a way of making sense of phenomena (Wells 2011). Furthermore, narrative inquiry is a communal activity involving the one who is inquiring (such as a researcher or interviewer) and the one who is responding (such as a participant or interviewee),

and where there is a shared responsibility to explore the object in question (Heldke 1988). The richness of data that narrative inquiry provides necessitates analysis that leaves room for the individual voices and their way of establishing meaning through storytelling (Josselson and Hammack 2021). The analysis focuses on patterns of meaning in the narratives but also seeks to reflect on the roles of the inquirer and the interpreter in accounting for these patterns.

When using narratives to understand food and eating in the context of individual recollection and historical memory, the researcher recognises that neither one nor the other presents a single truth. There is no model of inquiry that allows an uninterested or non-biased account of individual experience, meaning that individual testimony requires contextualisation and acknowledging that there is always a relationship between the inquirer, the inquired, and the object(s) being examined (Heldke 1988). Correspondingly, there is no straightforward definition of historically embedded cultural practices such as “national cuisines,” as they assert the existence of a homogenised cuisine separating those within the borders of a nation from those outside (Hedegaard 2018). However, individual voices may open layers of meaning embedded in their experiences, and how such experiences may relate to collective meanings, such as cultural heritage.

5.2 Culinary approach: Conceptual justification supported by existing evidence.

Food-memory workshops allow for a narrative-based exploration of the relationship between food, memory, identity, and cultural heritage. Research in food studies and anthropology has extensively shown that everyday food practices function as key mediators of memory, belonging, and identity formation, linking personal life histories to broader cultural frameworks (Holtzman 2006). However, narrative approaches alone risk privileging articulated and reflective knowledge, while leaving embodied and tacit forms of knowing less visible.

For this reason, integrating a practical culinary component is methodologically relevant. Cooking allows participants to engage actively with what they have narrated, making it possible to examine action nuances and challenges. Cooking enriches discourse and how the body itself acts as a repository of memory and knowledge. As Heldke (2018) argues, the action of making food is needed to fully understand food knowledge as a situated and practice-based phenomenon. Integrating cooking into food-memory workshops, therefore, raises a central methodological question: *Can cooking be understood as a form of inquiry?* In answering

this question, the Food Memories team frames culinary practice as both an object of study and, more significantly, as a knowledge-producing activity.

5.2.1 Integrating Cooking Practices as Methods

Cooking practices constitute one of the key mechanisms through which individuals perform, negotiate, and transmit both individual and collective identities (Sutton 2011). By integrating practice into the research design, the workshops deliberately bridge theory and praxis, or how knowledge is idealised or described, and how those ideals or theories are actually enacted.

Incorporating culinary practice makes it possible to augment the narrative dimension and explore how food memory and experience materialise in action. Food preparation makes it possible to observe how memories are reconfigured when put into practice, for example, how aromas, textures, and tastes translate into concrete decisions regarding ingredients, techniques, and sequencing; or how food knowledge circulates between participants through embodied skills rather than verbal explanation alone (Sutton 2010).

Likewise, the sensory experience associated with cooking (smells, textures, tastes) activates aspects of memory that might remain inaccessible in a purely descriptive or idealised form, thus integrating cognitive, affective or emotional, sensorial, and bodily dimensions in the construction of identity. We consider “identity construction” as the production of identities socially, culturally and historically mediated through the senses (Walmsley 2015). In this sense, the workshops function as a space of theory and praxis, where participants’ statements about their food identities are confronted with and enriched by practical experience, revealing the relationship between narrative, memory, and action.

5.2.2 Integrating Cooking Practice to Consider Historical and Future Dimensions

Within the framework of the RELISH project, Food Memories proposes to complement food-memory workshops with a practical component of a culinary nature. On the one hand, this approach considers that both the act of cooking and the discourses and narratives that emerge during practice constitute relevant sources of information for the project, including eating habits, expectations, knowledge of gastronomic heritage, techniques and cooking methods, the use of utensils and ingredients, the ways of obtaining them, as well as the typicality and flexibility related to what is considered “typical” or traditional, and its connection to the family, community, regional, or national sphere.

On the other hand, facilitating the culinary session makes it possible to project reflection and discussion about memory, history, and/or tradition toward a prospective dimension: beyond analysing the relationship between food heritage and innovation, the practical activity allows for an exploration of how this legacy may be transformed in the future. Recipe preparation thus becomes a methodological tool for identifying 1) continuities and adaptations within the culinary tradition, and 2) elements that participants consider important to preserve, modify, or leave behind in the future. Food Memories provides a perspective on the dynamics of cultural transmission and on the collective and individual decisions that will shape transformations and transitions in food heritage. Food Memories sees culinary practice as a dialogue between memory, innovation, and future projection.

5.2.3 Cooking Practice as Embodied or Tacit Knowledge

Following Goodwin (2016), knowledge is understood not only as something articulated through language or held cognitively, but also as something enacted through the body and situated action. In cooking practices, knowledge is expressed through how individuals manipulate tools, ingredients, and space. Gestures such as cutting, mixing, seasoning, or kneading involve continuous decision-making based on prior experience, even when these decisions are not verbally articulated.

These bodily actions reproduce culturally learned and socially transmitted forms of knowing that have been internalised through repetition and practice. Such knowledge is often automatised to the point that it operates below the level of conscious reflection. In this sense, bodies retain and activate memory through action, even when participants do not explicitly narrate it. In food studies, these forms of knowing are commonly described as embodied and tacit knowledge, both of which are central to the Food Memories methodological approach.

By incorporating cooking practices into the Food Memories workshops, the methodology enables access to embodied forms of culinary knowledge and food heritage that are not always captured through narrative or written accounts alone (Sutton 2001). Observation of cooking practices therefore complements narrative methods by revealing how knowledge is enacted rather than only described.

This approach is particularly relevant in relation to RELISH's focus on recipes. Examining cooking actions allows the workshops to explore the tacit dimension of recipes: that is, all the knowledge a recipe does not explicitly state because it assumes it is already known by the person preparing the dish. What a recipe leaves unsaid—techniques, judgments, sensory thresholds—is precisely what the reader is expected to infer from prior experience.

The sensory dimension provides a clear illustration of this tacit knowledge. Instructions such as “adjust with salt and pepper” or “mix until the desired consistency is reached” rely on forms of sensory judgment that are difficult to formalise in writing. Recipes presume that cooks know what an appropriate texture, flavour balance, or level of seasoning should be. The Food Memories approach starts from the assumption that this sensory knowing is culturally learned: individuals’ “organoleptic repertoires” are shaped by food culture, and culinary intuition—expressed through automatised gestures and sensory evaluation—embodies this learned knowledge (Sutton 2001).

6 Methodology

6.1 Narrative method

The Food Memories Workshops constitute one of RELISH’s central participatory methodologies. Situated within the broader collaborative framework of the consortium, the workshops adopt a co-creation–oriented research design that foregrounds storytelling, writing, and embodied engagement with food not only as sources of data, but as modes of joint knowledge production shaping both the research process and its outcomes in the field of Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH).

Drawing on life-writing, narrative inquiry, and cooking-as-inquiry), the workshops invite participants to articulate food memories through writing and cooking practices. These activities position participants as active authors of meaning: through selecting which memories to narrate, how to frame them, and which recipes or practices to enact, participants make interpretive decisions that directly inform the conceptual and methodological development of the workshops. Cooking and writing function here as generative research acts, through which participants translate embodied, affective, and situated knowledge into shared forms that can be discussed, negotiated, and reworked collectively.

Co-creation is enacted concretely through the dialogical structure of the workshops and their iterative design. Facilitated writing and cooking sessions are followed by collective reflection moments in which participants share narratives, compare interpretations, and identify points of convergence and divergence across their experiences. These exchanges do not merely elicit responses but actively shape subsequent workshop activities, prompts, and emphases. Insights emerging from participants’ discussions have been incorporated into revisions of the workshop

structure and into the development of the Food Memories manual, with participants influencing both thematic focus and methodological sequencing.

The workshop design is informed by action research and educational inquiry models that emphasise the cyclical relationship between planning, action, observation, and reflection. Within this framework, participants are understood as co-creators of knowledge insofar as their narratives, sensory experiences, and culinary practices inform not only the content of the research but also its direction and interpretive frameworks. This approach is further grounded in Freire's notion of language as transformative action: through dialogical exchanges conducted in horizontal relations of mutual trust, participants collectively name, question, and reinterpret culinary heritage, fostering critical reflection on how traditions, rituals, and preferences are shaped by social change.

In the Food Memories Workshops, co-creation thus operates through shared authorship, collective sense-making, and iterative methodological adaptation. Writing and cooking support this process by enabling participants to externalise tacit knowledge, negotiate meanings with others, and contribute to the collective construction of heritage narratives that may not emerge through conventional ethnographic or historical research methods.

In this pilot phase, the workshops engage emerging adults—particularly students participating in mobility programs such as Erasmus—whose transitory life situations offer a distinct perspective on how culinary heritage is reinterpreted, adapted, and renegotiated across geographical and cultural contexts.

In parallel, the Food Memories Workshops are intentionally developed as a methodology that can operate across disciplinary boundaries and be taken up by non-technical and non-scholarly facilitators. The workshop design and accompanying manual translate theoretical frameworks from participatory research, narrative inquiry, and heritage studies into accessible prompts, activities, and facilitation guidelines that do not require specialised academic training to implement. By grounding the methodology in everyday practices such as cooking, writing, and storytelling, the workshops create an entry point for facilitators and participants from diverse backgrounds—including cultural practitioners, educators, community organisers, and heritage workers—to engage meaningfully with questions of Intangible Cultural Heritage. This emphasis on clarity, adaptability, and experiential learning allows the methodology to function as a shared tool for interdisciplinary collaboration, while preserving the reflexive and critical dimensions necessary for research and heritage innovation.

6.2 Objectives and scope

The workshops are designed around several methodological objectives:

- To facilitate reflection on food-related memories as expressions of cultural heritage
- To explore the relationships between identity, mobility, and culinary continuity
- To support inclusive and participant-led forms of knowledge production
- To generate qualitative materials (texts, images, audiovisual recordings) for integration into the RELISH digital platform

Participants are encouraged to co-create recipes and narratives that reflect adaptation and change, while facilitators gather textual and audiovisual materials following shared ethical and methodological guidelines. The methodology is currently conceived as replicable across RELISH institutions, contributing to a shared repertoire of participatory practices within the consortium. Later, the methodology will also be developed further to enhance replicability for different of target audiences/spaces.

6.3 Workshop design and phases

PREPARATORY PHASE

Prior to the workshops, participants complete intake forms that assist facilitators in forming culturally and linguistically coherent groups. Ethical protocols are established at this stage: all participants provide informed consent for the potential use of text, images, and audio; their confidentiality is safeguarded; and Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, and Belonging (DEIB) considerations guide group facilitation. The workshop team typically includes a lead facilitator, a co-facilitator or assistant, and an audiovisual documentarian provided by each hosting institution. Creative materials are prepared for mapping and writing, and when possible, a kitchen space and the support of professional chefs are arranged for the cooking session.

Figure 12: Food Memories workshop design

6.3.1 Day 1: Mapping and Writing (Narrative Session)

The first day activity focuses (Day 1) on memory mapping and creative writing. The session begins with an introduction round in which participants share a food memory in an informal, conversational format that avoids intrusive questioning. They then move to the creation of a “food memory map,” a visual representation or foodscape linking ingredients, dishes, locations, events, aromas, and textures associated with their sense of “home.”

This mapping exercise lays the groundwork for a timed, free-writing activity in which participants develop narratives based on their maps. Facilitators emphasise uncensored recall and sensory detail, allowing participants to explore moments that emotionally resonated with them through writing. Passages of particular significance are highlighted for later revision initially by facilitators and through co-creation strategies, also by participants. For instance, a dialogue about the mapping and the narratives is the initial step as an icebreaker and preparation for the cooking session.

In the final phase, participants collectively engage with the notion of the “recipe.” They may either co-create a new recipe or reach a consensus around a recipe they wish to work with together. This process involves listing ingredients, negotiating differences in taste, traditions, dietary needs (including allergens), and ingredient

availability. Participants are also encouraged to speculate on how the recipe might change in the future, considering material constraints, cooking practices, and broader social or environmental transformations. The outcome of Day 1 is a shared recipe that will be prepared during Day 2.

6.3.2 *Day 2: Cooking, Sharing and Co-creation (Cooking Session)*

The cooking session, scheduled two to three days after the initial workshop (Day 1), provides an opportunity for participants to engage in collaborative culinary practice. Various formats are possible: one participant may lead the preparation of their recipe, while others observe and assist; or, the group may collectively cook a single dish. These modalities allow for multiple forms of interaction and reflection, depending on the researcher's initial objectives. These sessions, typically lasting four to five hours, foreground cooking as a form of knowledge-making.

Facilitators guide participants' attention not only to the technical aspects of cooking but also to the narratives and memories activated during practice. Particular emphasis is placed on the embodied dimension of cooking—the way gestures, movements, and sensory perception function as forms of tacit knowledge—and on sensory triggers of memory, especially smell and taste. Participants are encouraged to reflect on how they learned a recipe, what memories surface at specific moments, and which ingredients or techniques feel most intricately connected to heritage, adaptation, or belonging.

The session is documented through facilitator field notes and, where consent is granted, audio and video recordings. It concludes with a collective tasting and a shared reflection, followed by an initial evaluation in the form of a feedback roundtable.

6.4 **Methodological reflection and design constraints**

Considering the range and depth of information generated through the workshops, it is important to clarify the specific contribution of each phase. The first day—focused on memory mapping and creative writing—constitutes a complete and methodologically robust exercise in itself. It consistently produces rich and meaningful material aligned with the project's objectives and can function as a standalone food-memory methodology.

The cooking session, however, provides a crucial additional layer of knowledge. It deepens the material emerging from Day 1 by activating embodied, sensory, and

relational dimensions that cannot be accessed through narrative work alone. At the same time, experience from pilot sessions indicates that a cooking session conducted in isolation—without the prior memory-mapping and recipe co-creation exercise—does not yield comparable results. When participants engage in cooking without having first collectively reflected on memories, identities, and future-oriented questions, memories tend to remain less articulated, discussion is more limited, and connections between participants are less developed. Similarly, collecting recipes in advance without the shared negotiation process of Day 1 has proven to reduce participants' emotional and reflective engagement.

For these reasons, the methodology concludes that while memory mapping and creative writing can function independently as a Food Memories exercise, the cooking session should not be implemented as a standalone activity. Consequently, institutions without access to a kitchen space may implement only Day 1 without compromising methodological integrity, acknowledging that this choice limits the depth of sensory and embodied insights that only the cooking session can provide.

6.5 Follow-up and analysis

During the follow-up phase, participants may voluntarily continue revising their texts. Facilitators then conduct thematic and narrative analyses drawing on written materials, cooking-related narratives, observational notes, and audiovisual documentation. Selected materials are prepared for integration into the RELISH digital platform, and hosting institutions may organise public-facing activities such as exhibitions, readings, or discussion events to disseminate participants' contributions.

Ethical considerations underpin all stages of the methodology. Participation is entirely voluntary; individuals may withdraw or withhold sensitive material at any point. Anonymity is respected whenever requested. Particular care is taken when facilitating workshops involving migrants or minorities, recognising that food memories often touch upon intimate, emotional, or vulnerable aspects of identity. DEIB principles inform facilitation, group dynamics, and documentation practices to ensure cultural sensitivity, equitable participation, and a safe and respectful environment.

6.6 Data analysis methodology

The analysis approach adopted within the Food Memories workshops combines qualitative, interpretive, and multimodal methods, reflecting the narrative, sensory,

and embodied nature of the data collected. Given the participatory orientation of the methodology, data analysis is designed to respect participants as co-producers of meaning while ensuring analytical rigor, transparency, and comparability across workshop sites. Not all analytical methods need to be applied in every case; rather, those most relevant should be selected according to the specific objectives of each workshop implementation.

6.6.1 *Types of data analysed*

The analytical framework draws on multiple data sources generated across the distinct phases of the workshops:

- Written narratives produced during creative writing exercises and subsequent revisions
- Visual materials, including food memory maps and recipe drafts
- Audio or audiovisual recordings of group discussions, cooking sessions, and collective reflections, where consent is provided and filming equipment is available
- Facilitator field notes and observational logs
- Feedback collected during evaluation roundtables

These materials are treated as complementary and mutually informative, allowing for triangulation between narrative, sensory, and experiential dimensions.

6.6.2 *Analytical framework*

Data analysis is structured around three interconnected analytical axes. Where justified and appropriate, not all axes need to be applied; rather, those most relevant may be selected according to the objectives and context of the workshop:

- 1) Narrative and thematic analysis
- 2) Embodied and sensory analysis
- 3) Prospective and heritage-transformation analysis

Each axis addresses a specific dimension of the research questions while contributing to an integrated understanding of food memories and culinary heritage.

6.6.3 *Narrative and thematic analysis*

Written texts and transcribed oral narratives are analysed using qualitative thematic analysis, combining inductive and deductive coding.

The process begins with an inductive phase (bottom-up). This means that codes and themes are identified from the data itself, based on the words, expressions, and meanings that participants bring into their stories—without forcing them into predefined categories. Typical themes that may emerge include memory, belonging, family transmission, migration, adaptation, nostalgia, loss, or innovation.

The analysis then continues with a deductive phase (top-down). In this step, the themes identified inductively are organised and interpreted using a shared analytical framework, aligned with the RELISH conceptual focus. This helps ensure comparability across workshop sites. Relevant overarching categories may include identity construction, cultural continuity, hybridity, and food as heritage.

Beyond thematic content, the narrative analysis also considers how stories are told. This includes structural and linguistic features such as shifts between individual and collective voice (e.g., “I”, “we”, “my family”), temporal orientation (past, present, future), and emotional tone. This provides insight into how participants position themselves within personal, cultural, and culinary narratives.

Finally, cross-case comparison is conducted to identify both shared patterns and context-specific differences across groups, institutions, and geographic settings.

6.6.4 *Embodied and sensory analysis*

To capture dimensions of knowledge that are not fully articulated through language, the analysis applies an embodied and sensory lens, with particular attention to the manifestation of tacit knowledge during cooking practices. Facilitator field notes, structured observation grids, and (where consent and equipment allow) video recordings are reviewed to identify recurring gestures, routines, and decision-making moments during food preparation (e.g., tasting, seasoning adjustments, tactile assessment of texture and doneness). These moments often reveal practical, experience-based knowledge that is not explicitly verbalised.

The materials are examined by individual analysts using shared criteria, supporting analytical transparency and comparability across workshop sites.

Particular attention is paid to:

- Instances where participants rely on tacit knowledge rather than explicit instruction, identified through observation and supported by facilitator prompts (e.g., “How do you know when it is ready?”).
- Sensory references—especially smell and taste—associated with the recall of food memories, and how these memories are framed as individual, familial, or collective.
- Interactions among participants that suggest informal transmission of skills, including teaching, correction of techniques, and negotiated decisions during the cooking process.

These observations are coded using an adapted observational framework inspired by practice-based and sensory ethnography, focusing on how knowledge is enacted through the body and interaction with materials. This analysis allows for identifying embodied forms of culinary and heritage transmission that remain implicit or assumed in written recipes and verbal narratives.

6.6.5 *Prospective and heritage-transformation analysis*

A dedicated analytical focus is placed on future-oriented discourse and practice. Discussions related to recipe adaptation, ingredient substitution, sustainability considerations, availability of products, and imagined future versions of dishes are coded to assess how participants conceptualise the evolution of culinary heritage.

This analysis looks for:

- Explicit statements by participants about preservation, change, or loss
- Negotiated decisions and discussions between participants regarding tradition versus innovation, or continuity versus change
- References or negotiated decisions by participants related to environmental, social, or lifestyle-driven transformations

By analysing how participants imagine the future of their food practices, the methodology seeks to more openly capture aspects of heritage that integrate dynamic and negotiated processes of culinary knowledge transmission alongside attachments to, desires for, or ambivalence about heritage continuation or preservation. This approach directly addresses RELISH’s focus on heritage, innovation, and sustainability.

6.6.6 *Triangulation and validity*

Analytical validity is strengthened through systematic triangulation across data types and analytical axes. Written narratives are compared with observed practices; declared knowledge is examined in relation to embodied action; and individual accounts are contextualised within group dynamics. When all three axes are employed, regular analytical debriefings among facilitators enable reflexive calibration of interpretations and support the identification of shared analytical criteria across sites.

6.6.7 *Ethical handling and participant agency*

All analysis is conducted in accordance with informed consent agreements. Participants retain agency over how their materials are used, and any sensitive content is anonymised or excluded upon request. Wherever possible, participants are invited to review or comment on interpretative summaries, reinforcing the participatory ethos of the methodology, and ensuring that analytical outcomes remain faithful to lived experience.

7 Outputs and Integration into RELISH

Analytical outcomes include thematic summaries, annotated narratives, visual mappings of recurring motifs, and selected audiovisual excerpts. These analyses do not constitute content for the RELISH digital platform in themselves; rather, they provide a structured and documented knowledge base from which platform-ready materials may later be developed. The analytical outputs also function as shared working materials for other work packages, supporting ongoing interpretation, decision-making, and cross-analysis in line with the project's overarching objectives. The methodology is intentionally designed to be scalable and adaptable, enabling cumulative knowledge generation and iterative refinement throughout the project lifecycle.

7.1 **Data collection and analysis framework – Food Memories (RELISH)**

The analytical process is conceived as both *ex ante* and *ex post*. Prior to each workshop, a preliminary analytical framework is defined, including the key categories and concepts to be explored. This framework serves as a guiding template to support facilitation and to help steer discussions when relevant themes do not

emerge spontaneously during the workshop. Following the workshop, the analysis assesses the extent to which these initial analytical expectations have been met and identifies additional or emergent elements that expand, nuance, or challenge the predefined categories.

Table 2: Data Collection Framework

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE	DATA SOURCE	COLLECTION METHOD	ANALYTICAL APPROACH	MAIN OUTPUTS
Explore relationships between food, memory, identity, and cultural heritage	Creative writing texts; oral narratives	Memory mapping; free-writing exercises; group discussion (Day 1)	Narrative and thematic analysis (inductive and axial coding)	Thematic corpus of food-memory narratives; identity and heritage typologies
Understand food as a medium of cultural transmission across generations and contexts	Written texts; facilitator notes	Workshop observation; narrative exercises	Narrative structure and positional analysis (individual vs. collective voice; temporal orientation)	Analytical summaries on identity construction and transmission
Identify embodied and tacit culinary knowledge	Cooking-session observations; audiovisual recordings; facilitator field notes	Collaborative cooking session (Day 2); participant observation	Embodied and sensory analysis (gesture, routine, decision-making, tacit knowledge coding)	Documentation of embodied culinary practices; insights into non-verbal heritage transmission
Examine sensory triggers of food memory	Participant reflections; tasting discussions; observation data	Cooking, tasting, and collective reflection	Sensory analysis (aroma, taste, texture as memory cues)	Sensory memory patterns; links between organoleptic experience and identity
Analyse negotiation between tradition and innovation	Recipe drafts; group discussions	Recipe co-creation; ingredient and technique negotiation	Comparative thematic analysis	Mapping of adaptation strategies and cultural hybridity
Capture future-oriented perspectives on food heritage	Speculative discussions; recipe variations	Future-oriented prompts during recipe design and cooking	Prospective and discourse analysis	Insights on projected transformations of food heritage

Investigate tacit dimensions of recipes	Recipes; cooking practices	Observation of recipe execution	Practice-based and interpretive analysis	Identification of tacit knowledge elements absent from written recipes
Enable cross-case comparison across sites	All qualitative materials	Standardised documentation across workshops	Cross-case and comparative analysis	Comparative insights across regions and participant groups
Ensure participant agency and ethical integrity	Consent forms; participant feedback	Informed consent; feedback roundtables	Reflexive and participatory validation	Ethically validated data corpus
Contribute to RELISH digital platform and dissemination	Selected texts, visuals, audiovisual materials	Curated selection post-analysis	Editorial and interpretive synthesis	Digital content; exhibitions; public-facing outputs

8 Considerations / Beyond the Method / FAQs

The Food Memories methodology offers a flexible and scalable approach that can be adapted to a wide range of research objectives within RELISH and beyond. Although designed to foreground culinary memory as a form of ICH, the method can be recalibrated to emphasise different aspects of food heritage depending on the institutional setting, the participant group, and the thematic priorities of each workshop.

When applied to cultural heritage research, the methodology enables detailed exploration of how recipes and food memories connect participants to familial, regional, and European traditions. It supports the documentation of lived culinary heritage practices, highlighting both continuity and innovation. For research contexts concerned with identity formation or intercultural exchange, Food Memories offers a way to investigate how individuals reinterpret culinary traditions and negotiate belonging, especially when living or studying away from home. The approach is equally suitable for pedagogical environments, where creative writing and reflective exercises help students develop awareness of the cultural and historical layers embedded in everyday food practices. In community or artistic settings, the method lends itself to exhibitions, readings, and multimodal storytelling formats.

Early pilot tests of Food Memories conducted within the framework of the RELISH project—whether through cooking sessions, narrative sessions, or their

combination—have demonstrated that the methodology has the capacity to go beyond reflection on food heritage, recipes, and their preservation. Working through memory and identity has shown potential relevance for other fields of social intervention concerned with individual and collective wellbeing. Activating food-related memory can function as a tool of social prescription in contexts such as unwanted loneliness, memory-related illnesses, the identification of food-related needs in people living with specific pathologies, and the socialisation of older adults or other vulnerable groups. In this sense, within Food Memories, culinary heritage is not only an object of analysis in itself, but also a potential instrument for wider forms of social and cultural intervention.

The methodology is intentionally adaptable. The full format includes both a writing session and a cooking session, but each component can be adjusted to fit local conditions. Institutions without access to a kitchen may use a writing-only format, while others may extend the cooking component or incorporate additional rounds of reflection. Group size is typically designed to range between six and ten participants. Facilitators may choose to cluster participants by linguistic preference, cultural background, or academic program, depending on the workshop's aims. The recipe selection process also offers room for adaptation: participants may focus on everyday family dishes, regional specialties, holiday foods, or hybrid recipes shaped by personal experience. Facilitators can guide recipe choice based on ingredient availability, kitchen feasibility, or specific research interests such as sustainability, innovation within tradition, or adaptation to new food environments.

The work team can be scaled according to institutional resources. At minimum, workshops require a lead facilitator and an assistant; when cooking is included, a chef or kitchen facilitator ensures safety and supports participants' embodied inquiry. An audiovisual documentarian strengthens the quality of data collection, but optional when technical capacity is limited. Each team member can adjust their level of involvement depending on whether the workshop centres on creative writing, cooking, sensory analysis, or heritage interpretation.

Focal topics for observation vary according to research priorities. Facilitators may attend to embodied knowledge, sensory recall, intergenerational transmission, adaptation of ingredients, or the subtle ways participants innovate on inherited recipes. They may also focus on group dynamics, patterns of shared memory, or contrasts between regional traditions. Participant engagement can be tailored: participants may write in their preferred language, choose how much to share, and select whether to document emotionally sensitive memories.

Finally, implementation must account for institutional and cultural context. Each workshop site operates under its own ethical requirements, kitchen safety policies, and capacities for audiovisual documentation. Local food cultures may influence recipe choices and the nature of group discussion. The intended outputs—whether research materials, public events, or digital platform contributions—also shape how the method is applied.

Overall, the Food Memories methodology provides a coherent yet adaptable framework that enables researchers, educators, and cultural institutions to engage with European culinary heritage in ways that are locally grounded, ethically sound, and methodologically robust, while also opening pathways toward broader social, cultural, and wellbeing-oriented applications.

9 Beyond RELISH: Transferability and Broader Impact

The Food Memories methodology has been designed with transferability and long-term impact in mind. While its initial implementation sits within the RELISH project and focuses on European culinary heritage, the approach is conceived as modular, scalable, and adaptable to a wide range of institutional, social, and cultural contexts.

9.1 Transferability and social impact

Food Memories can be implemented across diverse sectors with minimal structural modification. In research contexts, it offers a robust qualitative framework for investigating food-related memory, identity, and heritage in unfamiliar cultural settings. In higher education, the methodology supports experiential and reflective learning, allowing students to engage critically with food systems, cultural diversity, and sustainability through creative and embodied practices. Cultural institutions may adapt the method for documentation, archiving, and public engagement initiatives, using workshops as sources for exhibitions, digital storytelling, or participatory collections.

The methodology will also be designed to be transferable to community-based and third-sector environments. Its modular design allows institutions to implement either the narrative component alone or the full narrative-cooking sequence, depending on available infrastructures and resources. Common facilitation guidelines, ethical protocols, and analytical frameworks ensure coherence and comparability across sites while allowing for local adaptation.

Pilot implementations have indicated that Food Memories holds potential beyond heritage research or preservation, particularly in the field of social wellbeing. By working with food-related memory and identity, the methodology has shown relevance as an instrument for social prescription and non-clinical intervention. Activating culinary memory can support initiatives addressing unwanted loneliness, facilitate socialisation among older adults, and contribute to wellbeing-oriented programs in community and care settings. This aligns with broader frameworks in which food is understood as a platform for systemic change in health care and community settings, exemplified by initiatives such as Nourish Leadership in Canada, which centres food as a powerful connection between health equity, sustainability, and community wellbeing.

Food Memories may also be adapted to contexts involving memory-related conditions, where food and sensory stimuli can support recognition, emotional anchoring, and communication in non-verbal ways. In health-oriented or social care environments, the methodology can assist in identifying food-related needs and preferences among individuals living with specific pathologies, enhancing person-centred approaches to nutrition and care.

Thus, within the Food Memories framework, food heritage is not understood solely as an object of study or preservation, but also as an active resource and methodological tool that can be mobilised in a wide range of social, educational, cultural, and wellbeing-oriented interventions.

9.2 Policy relevance and alignment with Horizon Europe priorities

The methodology aligns with Horizon Europe priorities related to cultural heritage, social inclusion, wellbeing, and innovation within the social sciences and humanities. By positioning food heritage as both a cultural asset and a social resource, Food Memories contributes to policy discussions on cultural sustainability, inclusive participation, and the role of culture in promoting quality of life.

Importantly, Food Memories reframes culinary heritage not merely as an object of preservation but as a living, actionable practice capable of generating future-oriented value. This positioning supports RELISH's broader ambition to connect heritage, innovation, and societal impact, while offering a replicable model that can be scaled across European contexts and beyond.

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Appendix I

Description: Updated facilitation guide and script for both the narrative and the cooking sessions.

FOOD MEMORIES WORKSHOP - PILOT 3

Welcome. This workshop invites you to explore how food, memory, and culture shape who we are—and how they might shape our futures. There are no right or wrong answers. You are always free to share as much or as little as you like.

Community Guidelines

- Sharing is voluntary; you may always pass
- Listen to understand, not to judge or fix
- Speak from your own experience
- Avoid assumptions about others' cultures, families, or access to food
- Respect confidentiality and care for one another

“Home” can mean many things: a place, a person, a culture, a community, or a moment in time.

Opening & Introductions

You will be invited to briefly introduce yourself and share a food memory connected to your upbringing.

Optional prompts:

- When you think of your upbringing, which tastes come to mind?
- Is it connected to a dish, an ingredient, a celebration, or an everyday moment?

Simple, ordinary memories are welcome.

Session I: Taste & Memory

Exercise 1: Food Memory Map – Tastes of Home

In this exercise, you will create a visual Food Memory Map.

What to include

- Foods, dishes, or ingredients
- Places (kitchens, gardens, restaurants, outdoors)
- Events or moments (holidays, birthdays, family gatherings, everyday routines)

All of these elements should connect to what feels like “home” or cultural belonging for you.

How to work

- Use paper or digital tools—whatever helps you express yourself best
- Draw connections between items to create a personal “foodscape”

- Be as detailed as you like: preparation methods, who cooked, smells, textures, emotions

If you're not sure where to start

- Where did these foods appear?
- Who were you with?
- How did they look, smell, feel, or sound?
- How did they make you feel?
- Close your eyes and recall one aroma or taste linked to a moment, place, or person, then build outward from there

You may use provided vocabulary cards to help name tastes, textures, and aromas.

Exercise 2: Free Writing – The Taste of Home as Cultural Heritage

This is a free writing exercise. The goal is flow and discovery, not polish or performance.

Guidelines

- Write continuously for the set time
- Do not stop to correct grammar or spelling
- Do not re-read or edit while writing
- If you feel stuck, write “I don't know what to write” until something comes
- You may write in any language you feel comfortable using

Use your Food Memory Map as a prompt.

After writing:

- Take a short break
- Return to your text and highlight parts that feel:
 - Surprising
 - Emotional
 - Personally or culturally meaningful

These highlighted sections can become poems, stories, essays, or journal entries.

You are welcome to continue developing this text between sessions, alone or with a partner.

Session II: Recipes for the Future

Reflection

We will begin by reflecting together:

- How did the previous exercises make you feel?
- How does food connect us to the past?
- How does it help us deal with nostalgia or longing?
- In what ways is food part of identity?
- Can food also help us imagine who we want to become?

Group Project: Co-Creating a Recipe

You will work in a small group to create a recipe that brings together elements of each person's culinary and cultural memories.

The goal: To imagine a dish that honours the past while thinking about the future.

Respect, curiosity, and consent are central. Dietary needs and boundaries should always be acknowledged.

Group Tasks

1. Find inspiration

- Share relevant memories from your writing and food maps
- Talk about shared flavours, ingredients, techniques, or rituals
- Research together if helpful
- Choose a dish concept that everyone feels comfortable with

2. Visualise the dish

- Draw, collage, or create a mood board
- Think about presentation and how the dish is eaten
- Consider where ingredients come from and how accessible they are

3. Research past, present, and future

- How were these ingredients or dishes used in the past?
- What innovations shaped how we use them today?
- Will this dish be possible in 10, 20, or 30 years?
- What might change—and why?

4. Draft the recipe

- List ingredients in the order they are used
- Break the process into clear steps
- Keep instructions simple and readable

Sharing

Each group will present their recipe and share:

- How it connects to memories and writing from Session I
- How they imagine this recipe changing in the future, and what that change might mean

Closing

To close, you may be invited to share one word or short sentence about what you're taking with you from this experience.

Thank you for being part of this shared exploration of food, memory, and possibility.

Facilitation script for the cooking session:

Previous dynamic focused on memory:

- Memory and experience through the senses
- The body holds unconscious knowledge, muscular and sensory memory
- How decisions are made in the kitchen through the senses

Reframing the dynamic towards the present and the future:

- What is there in this recipe that comes from an idea of family/cultural heritage?
- Why croquettes starting from writing? How did we arrive at this decision?
- How future-proof is this recipe?

Before cooking

1. Recap of Wednesday's experience using the maps
2. Brief comments on the texts that were created
3. How did we arrive at the recipe / the idea of making croquettes together?
4. Individually, sharing which aspect of your own rituals this recipe relates to

Facilitation script while cooking

For this session, we reused the script from Pilot 1 and 2 but added a section with observations and sensory questions, aiming to deepen embodiment and evoke non-conscious knowledge that the body brings out through the senses: e.g., turning off the heat when hearing rice crackling; checking the sauce texture to decide if more thickener is needed. Plus, we added a section about future scenarios and prospective.

1. How are we going to organise the work? Who does what?
2. Have you made croquettes before? When? With whom? Was it a particular occasion or something you have done regularly?
3. Imagine your life in 30 or 40 years. Which of these ingredients do you think you might not use anymore or might no longer be available?
4. Which aspects of your PCI or your heritage do you see reflected in the recipe?
5. How have you adapted this recipe to the future scenarios we discussed on Wednesday?
 - a. Absence of certain ingredients or products
 - b. Use of cooking robots
 - c. More food intolerances
 - d. Time constraints
6. Which sensory aspects – aroma, texture, etc. – make you think of other moments when you have cooked before?
7. On what occasion do you think we decided to make croquettes? Would you make them just for yourself?

Recipe / Preparation

- What does this recipe represent for you?
- Why did you choose it?
- Have you prepared it before? For yourself, family, or friends?
- When did you usually eat it? Was it everyday food or for special occasions?

Ingredients

- Were the ingredients you used the ones you wanted? Did you have to substitute any? Why?
- How and where did you source them?
- Was it difficult to find any of them?
- Would you say these ingredients represent your cooking or your food culture?

Learning and knowledge transmission

- How did you learn to make this recipe? At home, abroad, online...?
- How did you learn to cook in general? Who taught you?
- What has influenced your cooking more: family, friends, social media, or your curiosity to experiment?
- How would you describe your home cooking?
- Do you identify cultural aspects in what you cook?
- In your cooking, what weighs more: family environment or wider food culture?

Preparation

- How would you adapt this dish to different occasions, contexts, people? What could you substitute?
- Do you feel you are reproducing a culinary heritage? Consciously or automatically?

Consumption

- How is this dish served? Is there a specific way of presenting it?
- How is it eaten? With specific utensils, decorations, or rules?
- Do you eat it alone or with others? Does that change your experience?

Future perspective

- Do you think this dish will still be cooked in the future?
- Will it remain the same or evolve?
- What would it need in order not to be lost?

Senses

- Touch (texture): Does it have the texture you expected? The sauce? The meat? Did you notice by tasting or by another sense?
- Smell (aroma): Where does this smell transport you? Is it what you expected? Linked to a place, a person, or an image?
- Taste (flavour): Is the flavour what you expected? Does it always turn out the same? Is yours like your grandmother's?
- Sight (colour/appearance): Is this the typical colour and look? Does it resemble the version you know?
- Hearing (texture/processes): Did you use this sense? What do you think it adds to the cooking experience?

Appendix II

Description: Full “Initial Template” for the Food Memories manual (for internal circulation). – *See following pages for full document*

